

Systematic Review of Upper Extremity Outcome Measures Assessed in Randomized Controlled Trials of Poststroke Upper Extremity Rehabilitation in Low-to-Middle-Income and High-Income Countries

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Abstract

Objective

To systematically review randomized controlled trials (RCTs) of poststroke upper extremity (UE) motor rehabilitation interventions to identify the outcome measures used in studies in low-to-middle-income countries (LMICs) and high-income countries (HICs) and describe the differences in the context of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health.

Data Sources

Five databases “Embase, PubMed, CINAHL, Scopus, and Web of Science” were searched from 1960 to April 1, 2021.

Study Selection

Studies were included if they were (1) RCTs or RCT crossovers in English; (2) with ≥50% participants affected by ischemic/hemorrhagic stroke; (3) participants aged ≥18 years; and (4) used an intervention for the hemiparetic UE as the primary objective of the study.

Data Extraction

Title and abstract screening and full-text studies were reviewed, and data for included studies were extracted by two independent investigators. The study quality was assessed using the Physiotherapy Evidence Database scale. Data analyses were performed using SPSS (V29.0).

Data Synthesis

Of 5408 records, 1276 RCTs were eligible, 298 RCTs were conducted in LMICs and 978 in HICs. A higher percentage of RCTs in LMICs employed body structure and function outcome measures for central nervous system (eg, Fugl-Meyer Assessment) and tone and range of motion (eg, modified Ashworth Scale) as well as activity outcome measures for general activities of daily living (eg, Barthel Index). In HICs, a higher percentage of RCTs used body structure and function outcome measures assessing strength (eg, Motricity Index), activity outcome measures examining motor specific activity (eg, Action Research Arm Test and Wolf Motor Function Test) and dexterity (eg, Box and Block Test), as well as participation outcome measures (eg, Stroke Impact Scale).

Conclusions

There were significant differences in the outcome measures chosen for assessing poststroke UE rehabilitation interventions by researchers in LMICs and HICs. This suggests that there might be potential resource and expertise as well as timing constraints that influences the choice of outcome measures in RCTs between HICs and LMICs and highlights the need for

investigating the availability of resources, infrastructure, and expertise and their effect on the feasibility and practicality of employing different outcome measures in different countries.

Keywords

1. [Income](#)
2. [Outcome measure](#)
3. [Rehabilitation](#)
4. [Stroke Rehabilitation](#)
5. [Upper Extremity](#)